

FRIES REARRANGEMENT OF *m*-TOLYL ARYLSULPHONATES

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m-Tolyl benzenesulphonate, *p*-toluenesulphonate and *o*-toluenesulphonate undergo the Fries rearrangement when heated with anhydrous aluminium chloride to furnish in each case a mixture of *o*- and *p*-hydroxy-sulphones. The structures of all the sulphones, thus obtained, have been established by synthesising them unequivocally.

In continuation of our previous work (*Curr. Sci.*, 1953, 22, 307; this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 513) on the Fries rearrangement of arylsulphonates, the present paper deals with the rearrangement of *m*-tolyl arylsulphonates. The rearrangement, as in previous cases, did not occur to any appreciable extent below 100°. The temperature range of 130°-140° was found to be the most suitable, as charring occurred at higher temperatures.

The rearrangement of each of the arylsulphonates used in the present work resulted in the formation of both the *o*- and *p*-hydroxy-sulphones. *m*-Tolyl benzenesulphonate (I) yielded a mixture of 2-hydroxy-4- and 4-hydroxy-2-methyldiphenylsulphones (II and III). As a rule, the *o*-hydroxy-sulphone is more soluble in non-hydroxylic solvents than the *p*-isomer. This difference in solubility proved helpful in effecting their separation. The identity of the sulphones was established by their unambiguous synthesis.

The Fries rearrangement of *m*-tolyl *p*-toluenesulphonate was recently studied by Amin *et al.* (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1954, 13B, 182) and they reported the formation of only one isomer. They characterised this compound as 4-hydroxy-2:4'-dimethyldiphenylsulphone (IV) without furnishing any evidence. The present work has revealed that their compound is actually 2-hydroxy-4:4'-dimethyldiphenylsulphone (V). Amin *et al.* reported the melting points of their sulphone and its methyl ether as 144° and 132° respectively. 2-Hydroxy-4:4'-dimethyldiphenylsulphone and its methyl ether, which have been synthesised unequivocally, are found to melt at 145-47° and 131-32° respectively.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Fries Rearrangement of m-Tolyl Benzenesulphonate.—An intimate mixture of *m*-tolyl benzenesulphonate (49.6 g.) and powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (40 g.) was heated to 130° and kept at 130°-140° for 45 minutes. After cooling, it was decomposed with dilute HCl and ice. The oily substance separating was ether-extracted. The ethereal solution was then thoroughly extracted with a 10% NaOH solution. Acidification of the alkali extract furnished a product (11.6 g., 23%) which was found to be a mixture of 2-hydroxy-4- and 4-hydroxy-2-methyldiphenylsulphones. It was boiled four times with CCl₄ (30 c.c. each). The insoluble component was obtained as an oil. The CCl₄ extract on evaporation to dryness yielded 8.8 g. (18% based on the sulphonate used) of a substance which, on crystallisation from ethanol, melted at 124-25°, unchanged in mixture with the synthetic sample of 2-hydroxy-4-methyldiphenylsulphone (*vide infra*). (Found: C, 62.8; H, 4.7. C₁₃H₁₂O₂S requires C, 62.9; H, 4.8 per cent). The CCl₄-insoluble portion (2.5 g., 5%) solidified gradually on keeping aside for a week. It crystallised from benzene in plates, m.p. 119-21°, mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of 4-hydroxy-2-methyldiphenylsulphone was undepressed. (Found: C, 62.6; H, 5.1. Calc. for C₁₃H₁₂O₂S: C, 62.9; H, 4.8 per cent).

2-Methoxy-4-methyldiphenyl Sulphide.—To a solution of sodium ethoxide (2.3 g. of sodium in 30 c.c. of absolute ethanol) thiophenol (11 g.) was added and evaporated to dryness. The resulting sodium thiophenate was mixed with 2-iodo-5-methylanisole (Li and Adams, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 1565) (24.9 g.) and copper powder (2.5 g.) and heated at 200°-220° for 3 hours. After cooling, the dark brown mass was transferred to a flask and steam-distilled after the addition of H₂SO₄ (1:1; 50 c.c.) and zinc dust (10 g.) to remove any unchanged components. The residue was ether-extracted and dried (CaCl₂), and on evaporation of the ether 2-methoxy-4-methyldiphenyl sulphide (20.5 g., 89%) was obtained, b.p. 178-80°/8 mm. (Found: C, 73.1; H, 5.8. C₁₄H₁₄OS requires C, 73.0; H, 6.1 per cent).

2-Methoxy-4-methyldiphenylsulphone.—A solution of the above sulphide (4.6 g.) in hot glacial acetic acid was treated with excess of a 10% solution of KMnO₄ and kept aside for 20 minutes. The solution was then decolorised with SO₂. The sulphone which separated out (4.6 g., 88%) was crystallised from methanol as clusters of long needles, m.p. 15-56°. (Found: C, 63.6; H, 5.3. C₁₄H₁₄O₂S requires C, 64.1; H, 5.3 per cent).

2-Hydroxy-4-methyldiphenylsulphone.—A mixture of the above sulphone (2.6 g.) and HI (d 1.7, 8 c.c.) was heated at 200° for 2½ hours, cooled and then poured into water. The solid obtained was filtered off, washed with water and extracted with a 10% solution of NaOH. Acidification of the alkali-extract furnished the hydroxy-sulphone (2.1 g., 85%) in rhombic crystals, m.p. 124-25°, from methanol. (Found: C, 62.5; H, 4.9. C₁₃H₁₂O₂S requires C, 62.9; H, 4.8 per cent).

4-Methoxy-2-methyldiphenylsulphone.—A solution of 4-methoxy-2-methylbenzenesulphonyl chloride (Suter and McKenzie, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 2470) (11 g.) in CS₂ (30 c.c.) was mixed with AlCl₃ (anhyd., 10 g.). Pure benzene (3.9 g.) was added

slowly and refluxed for 1½ hours on a water-bath. It was then treated with HCl and crushed ice, and CS₂ removed. The resulting pasty mass (11 g., 84%) was washed with a few c.c. of methanol. It crystallised from benzene as needles, m.p. 92-93°. The same sulphone was obtained in 80% yield by the Friedel-Crafts reaction of benzenesulphonyl chloride with 3-methoxytoluene in CS₂. (Found: C, 64.5; H, 5.4. C₁₄H₁₄O₂S requires C, 64.1; H, 5.3 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-dimethyldiphenylsulphone was obtained in 85% yield by demethylation of the above sulphone with HI in the usual way. It solidified slowly. Crystallisation from benzene gave plates, m.p. 118-20°. (Found: C, 62.5; H, 4.5. Calc for C₁₃H₁₂O₂S: C, 62.9; H, 4.8 per cent). Vorozhtsov and Kuchkarov (*J. Gen. Chem.*, 1949, 19, 1943), who prepared it by the reaction of benzenesulphonic acid with *m*-cresol, reported m.p. 120°.

Fries Rearrangement of m-Tolyl p-Toluenesulphonate.—The rearrangement of this sulphonate, when carried out at 140°-150° as before, afforded a mixture of *2-hydroxy-4:4'*- and *4-hydroxy-2:4'*-dimethyldiphenylsulphones. The yield was 35%. The separation of the two isomers was effected by taking advantage of the greater solubility of the 2-hydroxysulphone in benzene. The fraction which was sparingly soluble in benzene, after several recrystallisations from toluene, gave the 4-hydroxysulphone, m.p. 151-52°. (Found: C, 64.0; H, 5.5. C₁₄H₁₄O₂S requires C, 64.1; H, 5.3 per cent). The fraction which was easily soluble in benzene, after repeated crystallisation from ethanol, gave the 2-hydroxysulphone, m.p. 145-47°. (Found: C, 64.2; H, 5.1 per cent). The identity of the two isomers was established by comparison with samples synthesised unequivocally (*vide infra*).

2-Methoxy-4:4'-dimethyldiphenyl sulphide was prepared by the reaction of *p*-thiocresol (12.4 g.) with 2-iodo-5-methylanisole (24.9 g.) as usual, and crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 62-64° (23.4 g., 96%). (Found: C, 73.8; H, 6.7. C₁₅H₁₆OS requires C, 73.8; H, 6.6 per cent).

2-Methoxy-4:4'-dimethyldiphenylsulphone.—Oxidation of the foregoing sulphide with KMnO₄ in acetic acid medium furnished the sulphone (4.7 g., 85%). It crystallised from ethanol in rhombic plates, m.p. 131-32°. (Found: C, 64.7; H, 6.0. C₁₅H₁₆O₂S requires C, 65.2; H, 5.8 per cent).

2-Hydroxy-4:4'-dimethyldiphenylsulphone was obtained by demethylation of the above compound and crystallised from ethanol as leaf-like crystals, m.p. 145-47°. (Found: C, 64.2; H, 5.1. C₁₄H₁₄O₂S requires C, 64.1; H, 5.3 per cent).

4-Methoxy-2:4'-dimethyldiphenyl Sulphide.—The reaction of 4-methoxy-2-methylthiophenol (15.4 g.) and *p*-iodotoluene (21.9 g.) yielded the sulphide (90%), b.p. 242-44°/30 mm. (Found: C, 73.5; H, 6.7. C₁₅H₁₆OS requires C, 73.8; H, 6.6 per cent).

4-Methoxy-2:4'-dimethyldiphenylsulphone was obtained in 90% yield by oxidation of the foregoing sulphide with KMnO₄ solution. It was also obtained (yield 80%) by the Friedel-Crafts reaction of 4-methoxy-2-methylbenzenesulphonyl chloride with toluene. It crystallised in needles from ethanol, m.p. 115-16°. (Found: C, 65.1; H, 5.8. C₁₆H₁₆O₂S requires C, 65.2; H, 5.8

4-Hydroxy-2:4'-dimethyldiphenylsulphone was obtained in 80% yield by demethylation of the above sulphone. First it separated as an oil but solidified gradually. Crystallisation from ethanol gave needles, m.p. 151-52°. (Found: C, 64.0; H, 5.5. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2S$ requires C, 64.1; H, 5.3 per cent).

Fries Rearrangement of m-Tolyl o-Toluenesulphonate.—The usual procedure was adopted. The alkali-soluble product (9.5 g.) was extracted with hot benzene when a black brittle substance was left, and discarded. Evaporation of benzene furnished 7.5 g. (29% based on the sulphonate taken) of a mixture of *2-hydroxy-4:2'*- and *4-hydroxy-2:2'-dimethyldiphenylsulphones*. The separation of the two isomers was effected with hot ligroin in which the 4-hydroxy-sulphone was almost insoluble. The ligroin-insoluble portion (0.25 g.), on crystallisation from ethanol, gave plates, m.p. 162-64°. (Found: C, 63.9; H, 5.5. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2S$ requires C, 64.1; H, 5.3 per cent). The ligroin-soluble portion (7.25 g.) crystallised from ethanol as plates, m.p. 142-43°. (Found: C, 63.8; H, 5.2. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2S$ requires C, 64.1; H, 5.3 per cent). The two isomers were identified by comparison with samples synthesised unequivocally (see below).

2-Methoxy-4:2'-dimethyldiphenyl sulphide was prepared from 2-iodo-5-methylanisole and *o*-thiocresol in the usual way. It crystallised from ethanol in fine needles, m.p. 59-60°. (Found: C, 73.2; H, 6.6. $C_{15}H_{16}OS$ requires C, 73.8; H, 6.6 per cent).

2-Methoxy-4:2'-dimethyldiphenylsulphone.—Oxidation of the foregoing sulphide (2.44 g.) in glacial acetic acid with $KMnO_4$ solution afforded the *sulphone* (2 g., 73%), which crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 164-65°. (Found: C, 65.5; H, 5.9. $C_{15}H_{16}O_2S$ requires C, 65.2; H, 5.8 per cent).

2-Hydroxy-4:2'-dimethyldiphenylsulphone was obtained in 74% yield by demethylation of the above sulphone with HI. It crystallised from ethanol in plates, m.p. 142-43°. (Found: C, 63.8; H, 5.0. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2S$ requires C, 64.1; H, 5.3 per cent).

4-Methoxy-2:2'-dimethyldiphenyl sulphide was obtained from *o*-iodotoluene (21.8 g.) and 4-methoxy-2-methylthiophenol (Suter and McKenzie, *loc. cit.*) (15.4 g.) as before; the yield was 22.5 g. (92%), b.p. 188-91°/13 mm. (Found: C, 73.6; H, 6.4. $C_{15}H_{16}OS$ requires C, 73.8; H, 6.6 per cent).

4-Methoxy-2:2'-dimethyldiphenylsulphone.—Oxidation of the foregoing sulphide afforded this *sulphone* in 82% yield. After crystallising from ethanol, it melted at 105-106°. (Found: C, 65.6; H, 6.0. $C_{15}H_{16}O_2S$ requires C, 65.2; H, 5.8 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2:2'-dimethyldiphenylsulphone was obtained by demethylation of the foregoing sulphone in 87% yield. It crystallised from ethanol in plates, m.p. 163-64°. (Found: C, 64.0; H, 5.2. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2S$ requires C, 64.1; H, 5.3 per cent).